

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RUEY****FIRST NAME: TETHLOACH****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word – 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The following two factors make the US English dominant in world English.

- The United States' global political and economic position.¹**
- The United States' demographic power and land mass.
- The United States' colonial history and land mass.
- All of the above.

2. Pure research addresses:

- A conceptual problem that has no practical consequences.²**
- A conceptual problem that has practical consequences.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

- Any complex problem.
 - All of the above.
3. The *Author-date style* is used widely in:
- Social sciences and in the natural and physical sciences.**³
 - Law.
 - Architectural studies.
 - Global Health.
4. The following is the study of the nature of value.
- Ontology.
 - Epistemology.
 - Axiology.**⁴
 - None of the above.
5. The following chapter helps the reader understand the dissertation's variables.
- The literature review chapter.**⁵
 - The method chapter.
 - The discussion chapter.

³ Ibid., 228.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your qualitative dissertation: a road map from beginning to end*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 146.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 31.

- The conclusion chapter.
6. It is a dissertation component that defends the research findings, discussions, and execution of procedures planned in the dissertation prospectus.
- Dissertation manuscript.
 - Dissertation.**⁶
 - Dissertation concept.
 - All of the above.
7. According to Thomas Schelling, strategy:
- Can be understood as the series of moves initiated by an actor (or actors) aimed at influencing the choice of an opposing actor, in a manner favorable to itself.**⁷
 - A general plan to achieve one or more long-term or overall goals under conditions of uncertainty.
 - Is a pattern in a stream of decisions to contrast with a view of strategy as planning.
 - Is a system of finding, formulating, and developing a doctrine that will ensure long-term success if followed faithfully.
8. The English style guide the European Commission uses is:

⁶ Ibid., 1.

⁷ Michael Andrew Berger, "How resisting democracies can defeat substate terrorism: formulating a theoretical framework for strategic coercion against nationalistic substate terrorist organizations" (PhD diss., University of St Andrews, St Andrews, 2010), 8, St Andrews Research Repository.

- Based on the standard usage of American and Britain English.
- Based on the standard usage of Britain and Ireland English.**⁸
- A European Commission English closer to the US English.
- A European English designed for non-English speakers.

9. Cultural diplomacy is viewed as:

- A practice undertaken to achieve normative, idealistic goals, is usually couched in terms of mutual understanding.**⁹
- A practice undertaken to achieve normative, idealistic goals, is usually couched in terms of individual understanding.
- A practice undertaken to achieve normative, realistic goals, is usually couched in terms of individual understanding.
- A practice undertaken to achieve normative, realistic goals, is usually couched in terms of mutual understanding.

10. Which of the following is correct when you make sound arguments?

- You base your reasons on evidence.**¹⁰
- You base your evidence on reason.
- A reason is a statement that leads readers to accept the evidence.

⁸ European Union, *English Style Guide*, (European Union, 2021), 4.

⁹ Simon Mark, "A Comparative Study of Cultural Diplomacy of Canada, New Zealand and India" (PhD diss., The University of Auckland, Auckland, 2008), 39, Auckland Research Repository - ResearchSpace.

¹⁰ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 59.

- Evidence is the data on which you base your claim.

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